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Strategic Innovative Marketing and Tourism

Navigating Global Trends and Managing
Challenges — 12th ICSIMAT, Olympus
Riviera, Greece, 2025

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Community-Driven Events as Engines of Destination Regeneration: Lessons from Practitioners

Sofia Gkarane

Abstract This study investigates how community-driven, small-scale events contribute to the regeneration of lesser known destinations, offering a vital alternative to mass tourism. It addresses the debate on the sustainable impact of events on local development, revealing more complex forms of regeneration, beyond temporary economic benefits. Our approach involves qualitative insights derived from 12 diverse Greek events, purposively selected by type and location. Responding to the limited research on practitioners' perspectives, particularly in regional contexts, the methodology includes semi-structured interviews with organizers, focusing on their experiences, goals, collaborations and challenges related to tourism development and sustainability. Thematic analysis identified key findings. From the lens of organizers, the results underscore the strategic contribution of these local initiatives to Destination Regeneration. Six core themes emerged: Activation of Local Spaces, Local Identity and Social Cohesion, Economic and Tourism Stimulation, Resource Limitations in Planning, Stakeholder Engagement and Legacy, and Continuity Challenges. Organizers emphasized how events revitalize destinations by enhancing visibility, improving overall attractiveness, fostering community cohesion, and providing economic boosts year-round. While stakeholder collaboration is important, resource limitations and the need for sustained follow-up are critical. These events, despite limitations, are powerful catalysts for economic revitalization, social cohesion, and place-making, with implications for regional development.

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1 Introduction and Literature Review

The role of community-driven, small-scale events as tools for destination development has attracted considerable academic and practical interest recently [1, 2]. For example, small-scale cultural and sport events have emerged as significant contributors to the tourism growth of lesser-known destinations as they offer a vital alternative to mass tourism models while also fostering sustainable development [1, 3, 4]. Community-driven events seem to play an important role in developing specific processes, practices, and capabilities which are essential for local sustainability and growth [5]. They are increasingly recognized for their significance in contributing to the long-term growth of tourist destinations and in strengthening social bonds and cultural appreciation [2]. Their potential lies not only in their ability to attract visitors year-round [3, 6], but also in their important role within the social and cultural life of a destination, which helps to generate intangible benefits [3, 7]. Indeed, their less tangible social dimensions are central to understanding how these events contribute to sustainable destination development; the long-term viability of special events can depend on their alignment with the social values of the local community [8]. Therefore, it is crucial to discern the interplay between an event's legacy, the host destination's image, and overall tourism development [9]. The success of small-scale events often does not rely on expensive infrastructure but rather on the commitment and enthusiasm of the local population and volunteers' efforts [1, 10, 11]. Nonetheless, economic benefits are often measured quantitatively, but event organizers' views may prioritize community cohesiveness and social impact over purely economic gains [8]. Despite the considerable growth and popularity of small-scale events, research has been slow in understanding their social, environmental, and cultural effects [11], particularly from the standpoint of those directly involved in shaping and managing these events [3]. To ensure successful event tourism, scholars highlight the need for deeper insights into the perspectives of the event's key actors [12]. In this context, a notable research gap concerns event organizers' perceptions of the diverse impacts of their events on local communities [1, 11].

This paper seeks to address the aforementioned gap by investigating how various small-scale Greek events contribute to local tourism development. Drawing directly on the perspectives of event organizers, this research provides an in-depth exploration of the strategic goals, collaborations, challenges, and outcomes associated with such events, with a particular emphasis on their impact on destination regeneration.

2 Methodology and Research Questions

This study adopts qualitative research approach to explore the contribution of community-driven, small-scale events to tourism development in Greece, based on data from 12 diverse events. These events were purposively selected to reflect variation in type (e.g., cultural festivals, running events, festivals, etc.) and location

(urban, rural, mountainous, coastal) in order to ensure the inclusion of a broad range of tourism contexts (Table 1). As there is no official list of community-driven events in Greece, a gap previously noted even in sport-specific contexts [13], event identification was based on publicly available online resources, local tourism portals, and municipal announcements.

For this exploratory study, the use of semi-structured interviews was implemented as the primary method to collect in-depth data, aligning with qualitative research methodology [14]. Interviews were conducted with key event organizers, all of whom held central roles in the planning and implementation of their events. Participants were selected through a combination of a purposive and convenient sampling based on their expertise, availability, and on the relevance of the event to local destination development.

The interview guide questions focused on understanding the participants' experiences and insights as concerns event planning and sustainable local development, and are as follows: 1) How do event organizers perceive the contribution of small-scale, community-driven events to the development of tourism for their lesser known destinations? 2) What kind of partnerships do they pursue in order to enhance

Table 1 Overview of examined event cases

Event name	Region	Event character
Cosmopolis festival	Kavala	Cultural festival combining music, dance, gastronomy, and exhibitions
DinoDay	Filippiada	Thematic educational and experiential event for children and families, focused on dinosaurs
Fiesta Voio	Voio	Cultural and music festival promoting youth culture, local identity, and creative expression
Horseback riding gathering	Serres	Equestrian event for amateur riders, with focus on local identity and rural tourism
Acheron fest	Epirus	Cultural festival aiming to highlight natural/cultural assets of the Acheron area
Serres music & art festival	Serres	Music and visual arts event focusing on modern youth culture and city branding
Serexpo	Serres	Regional trade fair aiming to promote local businesses, gastronomy, and entrepreneurship with a tourism dimension
Piroshki competition	Eukarpia, Kilkis	Cultural-gastronomic event organized by the Pontic community, with community bonding and heritage preservation goals
Lake Kerkini activities	Serres	Nature-based event series including birdwatching, hiking, and local gastronomy, organized by the business chamber
Climbing festival	Kalampaka	Sports tourism event promoting Meteora as a climbing destination, blending adventure and local culture
Night half-Marathon	Kilkis	Athletic event designed to promote the city and increase local visitor flows during low season
Traditional music festival	Filyra	Folk music event celebrating local traditions and musical heritage

the sustainability and long-term impact of these events? 3) What key challenges do they face in planning and sustaining their events?

Thematic analysis was then employed to identify patterns related and to interpret the significance of the findings for tourism development [15].

3 Findings

Derived from the data thematic analysis, the following framework (Fig. 1) visually and conceptually represents how community-driven events contribute to the destination regeneration, through the lens of the events' primary decision-makers. The framework revolves around Destination Regeneration as the main outcome, influenced by three core dimensions (activation of local spaces, local identity and social cohesion, economic and tourism stimulation); each of these dimensions is shaped by several contributing factors, as depicted below.

Destination regeneration is at the center of the framework, as the main dimension that emerged strongly across organizers' perspectives as both a motivation and a tangible outcome of their efforts. Respondents indicate that events indeed play a strategic role in enhancing destination visibility, reversing stagnation and fostering a renewed sense of place, particularly in their host regions, which often suffer from economic decline or tourism marginality. For instance, organizers of cultural and music events note how cultural activation reintroduced forgotten or underused urban and rural spaces to both locals and visitors. Also, they recognize that sport-related initiatives held in nature attract a significant number of visitors, even if only for a short period. These insights, which respond to the first research question, reveal that a core strategic goal among organizers is to reposit their destinations by leveraging local character and spatial uniqueness.

Through the analysis, three core regenerative mechanisms are identified: A) First, activation of local spaces emerges as a dominant theme. Practitioners emphasize the

Fig. 1 A practitioner-led framework for destination regeneration through community-driven events

importance of reactivating underused or overlooked public spaces and rebranding their areas to attract new audiences. For them, events have become tools for reframing local identity and showcasing hidden assets, as seen in examples like Acheron Fest and the Piroshki Competition, where food, music, and natural landscape form the backbone of visitor experiences. Initiatives like these not only bring people to the area but also contribute to the spatial and symbolic reintegration of forgotten places into the social and touristic life of the community. This activation stems also from their desire to counter local decline and foster a pride of place; the ultimate aim for them is to stimulate new forms of engagement with these areas for residents and visitors alike. B) Second, local identity and social cohesion are recurrent goals and perceived outcomes. Respondents describe their events as platforms that can bring communities together, reinforce cultural pride, and pass traditions to younger generations. The importance of citizen involvement and community enthusiasm is particularly evident in school collaborations, volunteerism, and the use of local stories and aesthetics. C) Third, economic and tourism stimulation is frequently mentioned, although sometimes seen as a secondary or indirect benefit. Organizers report increased revenue for nearby businesses, higher destination exposure, and extended visitor stays, particularly when events are aligned with broader promotional efforts. For instance, in the SEREXPO and Piroshki Competition, collaboration with chambers of commerce or local producers enhance the economic footprint of the events. However, some organizers acknowledge that while events temporarily improve tourism flows, their capacity to drive sustained economic change is constrained without follow-up efforts.

Moving on to the exploration of the factors that enable or hinder the above outcomes, the analysis revealed two key enablers: The first one is stakeholder engagement, referring to the degree of collaboration among municipalities, sponsors, associations, and civil society. Events with strong partnership, such as SEREXPO with the Chamber of Commerce or the Serres Music and Art Festival with local institutions, demonstrate greater stability, broader impact, and stronger integration into local development agendas. This also shows that effective collaboration is a key enabler of the activation of local spaces. The second enabler is the orientation toward legacy and continuity challenges. Organizers who view their events as long-term investments rather than one-off spectacles report stronger community ownership, repeat visitation, and institutional trust. For example, initiatives like Cosmopolis and Fiesta Voio intentionally built their identity over time, linking each edition to a broader narrative. Other respondents seek to embed their events in the annual cultural calendar or link them to educational and environmental initiatives with the view to increasing long-term relevance. Notably, the catalytic power of events (like sport ones), even at a smaller scale, can be found in their repetition, which helps realize benefits sustainably for the host community and its residents [16].

Yet, as repeatedly pointed out by participants, these mechanisms and enablers are constrained by resource limitations. In fact, this has been a cross-cutting theme echoed in nearly every interview. Practitioners express concerns about inadequate funding, bureaucratic delays, volunteer burnout, and lack of continuity in local governance support. These findings directly expose structural vulnerabilities that undermine the sustainability and scalability of destination regeneration based on local events.

4 Discussion and Conclusion

The above presented framework, emerged entirely from the insights of practitioners, demonstrates that small-scale, community-driven events have the potential to serve as strategic tools for destination regeneration, when supported by collaborative networks, community engagement, and effective resources management to achieve sustained impact. Recent evidence highlights the significant role of small-scale events in facilitating community recovery and destination regeneration, thanks to their capacity to generate diverse economic and social impacts for local communities [17], especially in post-crisis periods [18]. Crucially, to create synergies that align with the local needs and bring a broader impact, effective collaboration with the community is required [19]. Through careful planning and stakeholder collaboration, organizers aim to establish sustainable events that positively impact the community [20]. The results further demonstrate that these initiatives are not temporary happenings but they can act as catalysts for deeper social, economic, and spatial transformations. They are driven by local energy and fresh ideas, offering flexible solutions to ongoing problems such as seasonality (given that they attract visitors throughout the year), poor infrastructure, and disconnected communities. They create deep community connections which are vital for sustainable local development [21–23]. According to practitioners, these events are not only important to generate immediate visitor flows but are also able to activate previously underutilized local resources and reshape the perceptions of places for visitors and residents. The findings suggest that event organizers are not only facilitators of entertainment, but in fact, they act as informal agents of local development although they frequently manage challenging conditions like uncertainty, scarce resources, and limited support. Given that most participants of this study are in fact long-term residents and highly engaged with the community, they are motivated by goals of regional promotion and revitalization of the destination [10].

Overall, this study provides a foundation for a better understanding of how to effectively use community-driven events to renew and strengthen regional destinations, drawing insights directly from the experiences of their organizers.

5 Implications and Future Research Directions

At a time when many regional areas struggle to remain visible in an increasingly competitive tourism environment, the findings of this study suggest that the role of such events in destination regeneration deserves deeper attention. Thus, this paper carries significant practical implications for tourism planners, practitioners, and local authorities. Policymakers should create an environment that empowers local organizers and emphasizes the vital role of robust partnerships; they should also encourage all stakeholders to integrate a vision for enduring benefits that extends the immediate event. Besides, different types of events (e.g., cultural festivals, sport,

or gastronomic events) can help create destination regeneration in unique ways and activate previously underutilized local assets. As an official list for such diverse events in Greece is missing [13], this study underscores the importance of establishing one, to better leverage their contribution to tourism. From a theoretical viewpoint, this research provides a perspective on the reality of organizers, a voice that is often marginalized in broader destination development discourse. The suggested framework offers an understanding of how events directly contribute to, and even shape, the revitalization process of a destination, apart the economic benefits that they bring. Thus, it creates opportunities for further theoretical exploration into concepts such as place activation in tourism contexts.

It is important to acknowledge some limitations to this study. While it is rich in insight, it is solely based on practitioners' perspectives offering a single stakeholder perspective. Thus, its qualitative and exploratory nature limits generalizability. Future studies could incorporate the perceptions of other key stakeholders such as local residents, tourists, authorities, and businesses, to provide additional dimensions to the understanding of destination regeneration. They could also employ quantitative methods to complement the qualitative findings, for example, by surveying a larger number of organizers. Besides, future research could delve deeper into specific themes identified in this study, such as innovative strategies for overcoming resource limitations in event organization or best practices for ensuring event continuity and legacy.

References

1. Gkarane S, Vassiliadis C, Kotzaivazoglou I, Fragidis G, Vrana V (2025) Combating seasonality in regional tourism: a call to action through sport events and practitioner insights. *Tour Hosp* 6:66. <https://doi.org/10.3390/tourhosp6020066>
2. Malchrowicz-Moško E, Poczta J (2018) A small-scale event and a big impact—is this relationship possible in the world of sport? The meaning of heritage sporting events for sustainable development of tourism—experiences from Poland. *Sustainability* 10:4289. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10114289>
3. Gkarane S, Gianni M, Vassiliadis C (2024) Running toward sustainability: exploring off-peak destination resilience through a mixed-methods approach—the case of sporting events. *Sustainability* 16:576. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16020576>
4. Melo R, Van Rheenen D, Sobry C (2021) Sport tourism events and local sustainable development: an overview. In: Melo R, Sobry C, Van Rheenen D (eds) *Small scale sport tourism events and local sustainable development*. Sports economics, management and policy, vol 18. Springer, Cham pp 19–42. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-62919-9_2
5. Stevenson N (2020) The contribution of community events to social sustainability in local neighbourhoods. *J Sustain Tour* 29:1776–1791. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09669582.2020.1808664>
6. Fotiadis A, Stylos N, Vassiliadis CA (2021) Travelling to compete: antecedents of individuals' involvement in small-scale sports events. *Tour Recreat Res* 46:531–547. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02508281.2020.1808934>
7. Parra-Camacho D, González-García RJ, Alonso-Dos-Santos M (2021) Social impact of a participative small-scale sporting event. *Sport Bus Manag* 11:109–124. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SBM-12-2019-0119>

8. Xie P, Sinwald A (2016) Perceived impacts of special events by organizers: a qualitative approach. *Int J Event Festiv Manag* 7:50–65. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEFM-05-2015-0023>
9. Bazzanella F, Schnitzer M, Peters M, Bichler B-F (2023) The role of sports events in developing tourism destinations: a systematized review and future research agenda. *J Sport & Tourism* 27:77–109. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14775085.2023.2186925>
10. Fotiadis A, Stylos N, Vassiliadis C, Huan TC (2016) Advocation travel: choice of events amongst amateur (non-professional) participants involved in small-scale sporting events. In: *Proceedings of the global marketing conference, Hong Kong*, pp 1516–1530. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02508281.2020.1808934>
11. Gursoy D, Kim K, Uysal M (2004) Perceived impacts of festivals and special events by organizers: an extension and validation. *Tour Manag* 25:171–181. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0261-5177\(03\)00092-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0261-5177(03)00092-X)
12. Ruhanen L (2009) Stakeholder participation in tourism destination planning another case of missing the point? *Tour Recreat Res* 34:283–294. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02508281.2009.11081603>
13. Gkarane S, Kavoura A, Vassiliadis C, Kotzaivazoglou I, Fragidis G, Vrana V (2025) The role of organizers in advancing sustainable sport tourism: insights from small-scale running events in Greece. *Sustainability* 17:6399. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su17146399>
14. Kallio H, Pietilä AM, Johnson M, Kangasniemi M (2016) Systematic methodological review: developing a framework for a qualitative semi-structured interview guide. *J Adv Nurs* 72:2954–2965. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jan.13031>
15. Williams M, Moser T (2019) The art of coding and thematic exploration in qualitative research. *Int Manag Rev* 15:45–55
16. Kaplanidou K (2021) Sport events and community development: resident considerations and community goals. *Int J Sports Mark Spons* 22:53–66. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSMS-05-2020-0082>
17. Rossini L, Falese L, Andrade A, Federici D (2024) Exploring the socio-economic impact of small and medium-sized sports events on participants, tourism and local communities: a systematic review of the literature. *J Sport Tour* 28:197–220. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14775085.2024.2448940>
18. Nguyen VK, Blaer M, Pyke J (2024) “I Have the Feeling of Community Again”: the socio-economic impacts of small-scale events on community recovery. *Event Manag* 28:1–19. <https://doi.org/10.3727/152599523X16907613842156>
19. Pereira E, Mascarenhas M, Flores A, Chalip L, Pires G (2020) Strategic leveraging: evidences of small-scale sport events. *Int J Event Festiv Manag* 11:69–88. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEFM-07-2018-0046>
20. Tomino AC, Perić M, Wise N (2020) Assessing and considering the wider impacts of sport-tourism events: a research agenda review of sustainability and strategic planning elements. *Sustainability* 12:4473. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12114473>
21. Miller JJ, Martinez JM, Stoll JA (2024) Conducting a special small-scale sporting event: what motivates people to volunteer in a small city? *Manag Sport Leis* 29:1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23750472.2021.1980423>
22. Kavoura A, Buhalis D (2022) Online communities. In: Buhalis D (ed) *Encyclopedia of tourism management and marketing*. Edward Elgar, pp 379–382. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781800377486.online.communities>
23. Kavoura A, Patrikakis C (2022) Data crowdsourcing. In: Buhalis D (ed) *Encyclopedia of tourism management and marketing*. Edward Elgar, pp 785–788. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781800377486.data.crowdsourcing>

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